

Fabrication of bright white organic light-emitting devices with multilayer structure

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Abstract

We have demonstrated that fabrication and characterization of bright white organic light emitting devices with a multilayer structure.

The configuration of the device was ITO/NPB//DPVBi/CDBP:Ir(btp)2acac/Alq3/BCP/CsF/Al. By adjusting the proportion of the (DPVBi, and Alq3) light-emitting layer, white light with commission Internationale de l'Eclairage (CIE) coordinates of (0.30, 0.36) and maximum luminance of 2453 cd/m² were obtained at an applied voltage of 12V.

Introduction

Organic light emitting diodes(OLEDs) have attracted more and more attention for their various potential applications such as full color display, backlight for liquid crystal display(LCD) or next generation light sources, since Tang and Van Slyke demonstrated bright green OLEDs with a sandwiched structure[1]. In order to generate the desired white light, WOLEDs with various configurations have been proposed, such as (a) a multilayer device with blue, green, and red emission layers, (b) a doped device with a host material and blue, green, and red fluorescence dyes, (c) a single emission layer device with white emission materials, (d) excimer and exciplex emission, and (f) tandem structure[2-3]. Among these approaches, WOLEDs employing multi-emissive layer structure has advantages over other architectures in terms of efficiency and color controllability because the recombination current, singlet and triplet energy transfer and performance of each layer can be controlled by layer thickness, doping concentration and charge blocking layers[1-3]. In this study, we demonstrate a efficient white organic light emitting devices fabricated by the phosphorescent organic material Ir(btp)2acac doped in host material CDBP as a red emitting layer, green-emitting (Alq3) and blue-emitting 4,4'-bis(2,2'-diphenylvinyl)-1,1'-biphenyl(DPVBi) layers were fabricated.

Experimental

The configuration of the devices is ITO/N,N'-bis-(1-naphthyl)-N,N'-biphenyl-1,1'-biphenyl-4,4'-diamine(NPB)(20nm)/DPVBi(xnm)/CDBP:5%Ir(btp)2acac(35 nm)/Alq3(y nm)/BCP(5 nm)/CsF(1 nm)/Al (150 nm), NPB acted as hole transporting layer(HTL), BCP as electron transporting layer, hole blocking layer(ETL/HBL). All devices were grown onto a pre-cleaned ITO coated glass substrate with resistance of 20 Ohm/sq. The ITO coated substrates were routinely cleaned with detergent, distilled water, acetone, and 2-propanol and subsequently in ultrasonic bath. The substrates were dried in an oven at 100 °C, before treatment with UV-Ozone. After treatment UV-Ozone for 25 minutes, all organic layers were deposited in succession without

breaking vacuum (10⁻⁶ Pa). Thermal deposition rates for organic materials, CsF and Al were 2 Å/S, 1 Å/S and 10 Å/S respectively.

Results and Discussion

Fig.1(a) shows the EL spectra with two different thickness of DPVBi. The dependence of thickness was observed with the blue color increasing related to the red light at increasing the thickness of DPVBi. The EL spectra peaks at 508 nm, due to DPVBi, peak at 618 nm, due to CDBP- Ir(btp)2acac. In the structure of ITO/(NPB) (20 nm)/DPVBi(xnm)/CDBP:5%Ir(btp)2acac(35nm)/Alq3(nm)/BCP(5 nm)/CsF(1 nm)/Al (150 nm), x= 20 nm and 30 nm, the CIE coordinates (0.39, 0.40) and (0.38, 0.47) were observed respectively.

Fig.1 Normalized EL spectrum of the devices

Fig.1(b) shows the EL spectra with different thickness of Alq3. The device structure ITO/(NPB) (20 nm)/DPVBi(20 nm)/CDBP:5% Ir(btp)2acac(35 nm)/Alq3(y nm)/BCP(5 nm)/CsF(1 nm)/Al (150 nm), we can observed that the red shifted with increasing Alq3, the CIE coordinates was observed (0.30, 0.36), its closet to the absolute white (0.33, 0.33) with the thickness of 25nm. The maximum luminance was 2453 cd/m² at 14V and 1662 cd/m² at 13V respectively(not shown here). When the CIE coordinates (0.30, 0.36) was close to the absolute white at 12V, its luminance was 2453 cd/m². We also observed that different thickness of Alq3 layer makes different efficiency and the optimum thickness is 25 nm.

References

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